

Deep Learning Over Multi-Field Categorical Data – A Case Study on User Response Prediction - Study on Reproducibility

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ABSTRACT

As the problem of predicting click-through rates and conversion rates is critical in many web applications, tackling the task of dealing with multi-field categorical data involves tedious work. In order to overcome this, Zhang et al. [2016] proposed two novel models based on Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) used to learn relevant patterns and make pertinent predictions of the users' ad clicks. Our work involved the reproducibility of the mentioned paper, by trying to follow the official implementations and then enhancing them with other repositories from extended and up-to-date repositories on the same topic.

CCS CONCEPTS

• **Computing methodologies** → **Machine learning.**

KEYWORDS

datasets, neural networks, Factorisation Machines, Stochastic Gradient Descent, click-through rates, conversion rates, reproducibility

1 INTRODUCTION

Estimating click-through rates is an important challenge as most businesses consider predicting user behavior a top priority. Simpler linear models such as the Logistic Regression(LR) are dominant in this field, but certain limitations have been observed. The deep neural networks models (DNNs) proposed by the authors tackle these limitations using transformation methods such as factorization machines (FMs), restricted Boltzmann machines (RBMs) and denoising auto-encoders (DAEs).

Our goal was to analyse the results on the paper by Zhang et al. [2016] and try to reproduce their investigations. We will broadly present their proposed solutions, describe their experimental setup and go through their results. Afterwards we discuss our reproducibility approach, our results and a comparison between the the implementations.

1.1 Zhang et al. [2016] solution

1.1.1 Logistic Regression (LR). The authors decided to use Logistic Regression as a baseline for the model comparison. Logistic Regression uses binary features converted through one-hot encoding from the initial data. The advantage that this model has is its fast and efficient learning, but, because it is unable to find patterns between the independent features, it doesn't perform very well.

1.1.2 Factorisation-Machine (FM). Factorisation Machine is a non linear model that uses a feature vector in order to predict the interaction between any two categories. It is regarded as one of

the improved embedding models and, furthermore, it can be upgraded/modified fairly easily. Its main advantage is the capability of estimating these interactions even when applied on sparse data.

1.1.3 Factorisation-Machine supported Neural Network (FNN). The first model proposed by the authors is based on the FM model, using it for the bottom layer. The neural networks layers above will learn more efficiently, as mentioned by the authors.

1.1.4 Sampling-based Neural Network (SNN). Finally, their last proposed algorithms were based on Sampling-Based Neural Networks (SNN): SNN-RBM and SNN-DAE. Restricted Boltzmann Machine(RBM) and Denoising Auto-Encoder(DAE) were used in order to compute and initialize the bottom layer's weights.

1.2 Zhang et al. [2016] experimental setup

For the hyperparameter tuning, the authors used the Stochastic Gradient Descent Model (SGD). They made use of early-stopping (the training stops when the validation error increases) and tried different values for the learning rate varying from 0.0001, 0.001, 0.01 to 1 and then choosing the one with the optimal performance on the validation dataset.

In the case of the activation functions, the authors chose the tanh after trying linear, sigmoid and tanh, as they found the results to be optimal.

In terms of architecture, the authors investigated models with 3, 4 and 5 layers and they concluded that the models with 3 hidden layers (5 in total) are the best, in terms of the area under the ROC curve (AUC) performance and they found that the diamond shape network outperforms the other analysed architectures from Fig. 1, for a total hidden unit size of 600 (200, 300 and 100 networks for each hidden layer respectively).

Figure 1: Network Architectures by Zhang et al. [2016]

The authors chose as an evaluation metric for the performance of the CTR estimation of each model the area under the ROC curve (AUC). Even though they also tried the root mean square error (RMSE), they noticed that the positive/negative examples are highly unbalanced in ad click scenario and the best regression model usually predicts the CTR close to 0 (which results in small RMSE values).

The authors provide the repository with the official implementation ¹. This contains a sample dataset and also all the implementations of the mentioned models (LR, FM, FNN, SNN-DAE and SNN-RBM). The code is custom-made for the provided demo data and the implementation doesn't cover the whole iPinYou dataset.

Moreover, the codebase is outdated, there are multiple dependency problems and we found various bugs when trying to run it.

1.3 Zhang et al. [2016] results

It is observed that the proposed models perform slightly better than the traditional solutions. However, taking the computation time into consideration, Logistic Regression and Factorisation Machines could still be favorites, as the differences between the runtimes is significant. While LR and FM finish their computation after several minutes, FNN and SNN take several hours to run locally. Furthermore, from a financial point of view, companies would not consider changing their proven models for an estimated improvement lower than 2% on average.

Campaign	LR	FM	FNN	SNN-DAE	SNN-RBM
1458	70.42%	70.21%	70.52%	70.46%	70.49%
2259	69.66%	69.73%	69.74%	68.08%	68.34%
2261	62.03%	60.97%	62.99%	63.72%	63.72%
2297	60.77%	60.87%	61.41%	61.58%	61.45%
3386	80.30%	79.05%	80.56%	79.62%	80.07%
all	68.81%	68.18%	70.70%	69.15%	69.15%

Table 1: Results by Zhang et al. [2016]

2 DATASET DESCRIPTION

Zhang et al. [2016] used the iPinYou dataset described by Liao et al. [2014]. As we couldn't succeed to download the dataset from the provided links, we managed to find it on kaggle ².

The dataset is the result of a competition from 2013 based on the global real-time bidding (RTB) algorithm by the Chinese online advertising platform iPinYou. It contains 19.5 million entities and the dataset is organised by the different advertisers, in a row-per-record format.

As Zhang et al. [2016] used a different structure of the data, than the original one, we needed to pre-process. We tried using the recommended repository ³ provided by Zhang et al. [2015], but this was problematic as it was producing a messy data structure with different numbers of features for each observation. Having the data in a different shape was problematic for the models. In order to overcome this problem, we searched for other implementations

¹<https://github.com/wnzhang/deep-ctr>

²<https://www.kaggle.com/lastsummer/ipinyou>

³<https://github.com/wnzhang/make-ipinyou-data>

and we used another version of the repo ⁴ which produces the 16 features in the right format for the training.

Following the experiments of the authors, we focused on the following campaigns: 1458, 2259, 2261, 2997, 3386 and all (the whole dataset).

3 REPRODUCIBILITY

3.1 Experimental setup

Our code and the implemented models can be found in the following GitHub repository ⁵.

3.1.1 LR, FM, FNN. As the use of the demo models from the official repository had dissatisfactory results, we implemented the models from another GitHub repository ⁶, which has a different version for the distributed trainings. This model is based on a paper by Qu et al. [2018] and is an improved version of the original paper by . We couldn't use the GPU optimization for the LR, FM and FNN models with this repository. For the conversion of the data into the hdf format, we used another repository ⁷. In order to use this repo, we only modified the path variables in the *Dataset.py* and *iPinYou.py* files for the training on each dataset. Furthermore, we set the 'initialized' variable in the *iPinYou.py* function to **False** in order to first generate the hdf files.

3.1.2 SNN-DAE, SNN-RBM. For these models, we used the scripts provided in the official repository ⁸. Nonetheless, there were needed some minor modifications, such as the train path and the x_{dim} variable (the maximum number of features of the advertiser - length of *featureIndex_file* + 1). These models have a high computational cost (especially SNN-RBM), as reaching the *init weights* takes around 7h for SNN-DAE and 8-15h for SNN-RBM, depending on the size of the selected dataset. Possible explanations of this could be that the models might be sensitive to hypertuning, or there might be some specific parameters that needed to be changed for specific datasets (we didn't find anything in our analysis).

3.1.3 Parameters. For optimization a Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD), as Zhang et al. [2016], with a learning rate of 0.1 or 1, the batch size equal to 1000 and generally 80 epochs. As it seems to overfit (the test results start decreasing significantly) we wanted an early stop. In the cases of LR, FM and FNN, we stop it manually (as the repository we used didn't have early-stopping implemented) and for the SNN model we used the internally implemented early-stopping feature. As activation function, we used the tanh, as recommended by the authors and for the architecture we chose a model with 3 hidden layers (5 in total) with a diamond shape network for a total hidden unit size of 600 (200, 300 and 100 networks for each hidden layer respectively).

3.2 Encountered difficulties

Our initial approach involved using the official repository. As seen in Table 2, our results were visibly worse than the ones reached by Zhang et al. [2016]. As the data structure resulted from the

⁴<https://github.com/Atomu2014/make-ipinyou-data>

⁵<https://github.com/matyasg/experimental-ex2-gr50.git>

⁶<https://github.com/Atomu2014/product-nets>

⁷<https://github.com/Atomu2014/Ads-RecSys-Datasets>

⁸<https://github.com/wnzhang/deep-ctr>

implementation of the recommended repository was chaotic, the models couldn't generate valuable results and our intermediary performance values were lower than expected.

After finding a better implementation of the pre-processing and also an improved version of the models, we attained similar results to the paper. Nonetheless, even if we succeeded in doing multiple sets of runs for each campaign (each run having a high computational cost), they weren't run with the same code, therefore we couldn't apply any relevant statistical testing methods.

Campaign	LR	FNN	SNN-DAE
1458	45.99%	62.16%	50.00%
2259	57.75%	61.90%	50.00%
2261	59.82%	54.80%	50.00%
2297	57.67%	61.02%	50.00%
3386	66.25%	68.16%	50.00%
all	-	-	-

Table 2: Intermediary Results - using recommended repository

3.3 Results

As it can be seen in Table 3, the results are almost identical as the ones stated in the paper, except for the SNN-RBM ones. The results for the *all* dataset are mainly better, higher with aprox. 5%, but in the case of the results for advertiser 3386, the LR and FM models performed slightly worse. This could be explained by our implementation of the basic model and not of the fine-tuned one (as we didn't have access to the tuning parameters), or by the limitations and the complexity of the implemented models.

Campaign	LR	FM	FNN	SNN-DAE	SNN-RBM
1458	69.10%	69.15%	69.81%	69.94%	-
2259	69.34%	69.02%	69.07%	66.47%	58.88%
2261	62.82%	62.25%	63.56%	64.24%	56.58%
2297	60.75%	60.77%	60.94%	59.44%	53.37%
3386	75.61%	75.87%	79.51%	79.51%	-
all	74.64%	74.60%	76.25%	-	-

Table 3: Final Results

3.4 Discussion

Following the initial paper's instructions and repository, we could not emulate the results. For each model, their performance was almost 15 percent lower than the one stated in the research paper. We consider that most likely various errors occurred during the preprocessing of the data. Furthermore, most models could not be run as they were using deprecated methods and libraries. However, after discovering the authors' updated research paper and using its preprocessing methods and algorithms, we managed to have the same results for the majority of the cases, with some exceptions for dataset 3386.

As can be seen in Tables 4 and 5, our final results have an improved performance and can better reproduce the results from the paper, even though there are still some differences.

Adv.	LR		FM	
	Paper	Ours	Paper	Ours
1458	70.42%	69.10%	70.21%	69.15%
2259	69.66%	69.34%	69.73%	69.02%
2261	62.03%	62.82%	60.97%	62.25%
2297	60.77%	60.75%	60.87%	60.77%
3386	80.30%	75.61%	79.05%	75.87%
all	68.91%	74.64%	68.18%	74.60%

Table 4: Comparison of the results for the LR and FM models

As we focused our effort on the implementation of multiple repositories, with various pre-processing methods in order to improve the performance results, we overlooked some of the costly runs. Therefore the missing data from the Tables 4 and 5 is caused by the extensive runtime needed for each of those models.

Adv.	FNN		DAE		RBM	
	Paper	Ours	Paper	Ours	Paper	Ours
1458	70.52%	69.81%	70.46%	69.94%	70.49%	-
2259	69.74%	69.07%	68.08%	66.47%	68.38%	58.88%
2261	62.99%	63.56%	63.72%	64.24%	63.72%	56.58%
2297	61.41%	60.94%	61.58%	59.44%	61.45%	53.37%
3386	80.56%	79.62%	79.62%	79.51%	80.07%	-
all	70.70%	76.25%	69.15%	-	69.15%	-

Table 5: Comparison of the results for the FNN and SNN models

4 CONCLUSIONS

With a lacking documentation and bugs in most provided scripts, emulating this experiment emerged as a difficult task. The mathematical aspect of the paper was thoroughly described by the authors, in detriment of the Github repository that did not have sufficient information in order to be successfully run without further information.

To sum up, the original research paper couldn't be reproduced easily and, without finding the updated versions, we would have been probably stuck with the intermediary results. Furthermore, the results presented by Zhang et al. [2016] don't show significant improvements compared to simpler models (e.g. Linear Regression and the Factorisation Machine), but they have increased runtimes. In our opinion, the trade off between performance and the computational resources isn't meaningful.

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